

ADVANTAGES OF USING PEDAGOGIC METHODS IN TRAINING STUDENTS AND YOUNG PEOPLE IN PHYSICAL EDUCATION

Durdona Abdurayimova

Tashkent state Uzbek language and literature university support PhD student

E-mail: Abdurayimovadurdona21@gmail.com

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8081015>

Abstract. In the course of the forensic investigation, the significance of the fields and psychological-linguistic methodology is discussed.

Keywords. Methodology, psychological, linguistics, verbal communication, non-verbal communication.

Of the century to their heads and the internet network development with whole in the world court the examination in processes important the facts being service who does oral and written resources , audio video and chat texts this to processes clarity input for to the object turning around is going Court in processes object being service doing oral and written texts analysis in doing linguistics with together psychology refer to the field as well to do must will be Court in the process concrete processes apply for complicated linguistic and psychological court expertise appointment and special experts attraction to do important importance occupation is enough Court processes that's it shows that complex inspection can't be it is oral and written texts on inspection one field specialist or of the court himself this processes determine can't or determine very complicated , therefore for such offenses determination for known of fields qualified from specialists consists of has been complex inspection group must will be.

Court expertise complex psychological -linguistic methodology work exit the examination processes one so much easy analysis to do for important is considered Court expertise complex psycholinguistic in methods concept and goals important is considered "Специфика такого рода судебной экспертизы, как **судебная психолого-лингвистическая экспертиза**, заключается в ее комплексности, в направленности ее лингвистических и психологических результатов на повышение объективности и всесторонности решения юридически значимой проблемы, следовательно, и в большей доказательности." [20. 06. 2023].

A court indeed in the process forensic psychological and linguistic of expertise this of type important has been aspect complicated and complex analysis do it take not only legal important have has been problems , maybe social to life circle has been many problems analysis in doing important is counted . Har how in the field methodology important calculated such as in this too methodology and methodology big importance occupation is enough This in the field methodology work exit for psychology and of linguistics from the methods is used , that's it with together , the theory work on the way out initially of practices , that is of experiences place incomparable is considered

Your personalities spiritual status their verbal and non-verbal in their actions manifestation will be Verbal communication in the process person using linguistic units

important considered his speech in the process accent, voice tone, pauses, how word and from expressions usage, syntactic devices how use etc vital considered non-verbal in the process while his face, eye, lip, eyebrow, hand and the body hints important is considered. Of persons spiritual status not only in, in the word, perhaps his external in the world, that is the body evident in his actions manifestation will be Nonverbal in touch person another one person can humiliate, insult, insult. So circumstances to be possibly non-verbal than verbal communication process more emotional effect to do can. Speaking of the process this features analysis to do of the person approximate portrait in drawing important is considered. Such analysis to do wide comprehensive and violations – determination and determined to offenders remedy in sight concrete to the facts relies on.

" Wide comprehensive psychological and linguistic forensic expertise during oral and written of speech investigation and court practice for important has been the following features defined as :

- 1) non-verbal (verbal speech for);
- 2) semantic-grammatical (phrases nature, word and of constructions selection, expressiveness size, correctness, text organize to be done and others);
- 3) categorical (gender, age, social position, profession, region, nationality and others);
- 4) pragmatic (goal, intention, reaction and others);
- 5) pathological (mental disease signs and morbid states of psyche)" [3.357].

Judicial investigation in the process such methodology structural in parts the first feature semiotics to the field the fourth feature to pragmatics and fifth feature psychotherapy to the fields appeal to do Demand does. Such complicated system a lot edged problems in solving big service does. From this It seems that the judicial investigation process persons with depends that it was for his speech, psychology, purpose, even medical situation determination for one how much fields they catch and the only one court process for service does.

This method social network correspondence also apply on because it is possible social network person in correspondence as well the spirit and his linguistic knowledge manifestation will be Social word of mouth on the net as well and written speech there is is written speech analysis to do hand writings analysis from doing a little different will be. In this process main attention correspondence phonetics, style focused, but methodology does not change.

Methodical research in the process each one aspect according to research will be done. " Pragmatic in aspect speech statement seeing will be released. contact needs with determined contact unit as and language of activity socio-historical context. Cognitive in terms of linguistics, speech and speech activity again work is a type linguistic tools with coded information, cognitive process [2.355]. Such wide comprehensive in aspect research to be done paralyzed and content proportionality reason will be Person a lot edged creature that it was his to psychology different objective and subjective factors effect as a result in the psyche changes his linguistic, psychological, pragmatic such as one series in aspects to be studied Demand does.

" Psycholinguistic forensic medicine in practice main analysis subject oral or written speech of products linguistic and paralinguistics parameters they are investigation, inquiry and of the court one series to the questions answer gives " [21.06.2023].

Of these himself two type divided into :

- Simple questions ;
- Complex questions .

" Simple questions :

- Communicators of the conversation main topics of what consists of;
- Communicators conversations topic and purpose what ;
- Communicators in conversation participation reach level how ... "[21.06. 2023].

Simple analysis complicated of analysis initial stage being service to do with next to stage road map prepares .

" Complex psycholinguistic of criminology common method the examination of speech psychological features from detection consists of

Oral of speech official and informal linguistic and paralinguistics features learning based on communication of the doers behavior whole psychological speech again Create for written text placed questions with depends without of communicators portraits to form service does "[21.06. 2023].

Summary as that's it we say maybe so complex of methodology work output form and content proportionality surface cause , judicial investigation in the process the examination consistent , reliable , intensive , proven and concrete to be provides . That's it with together of the field in development one how much specialists cooperation and this areas intersection problematic circumstances eliminate to do service does Suspect person or guilty individuals in determining important only not only to them to be given relief and punishment measures appointment or unknown criminals to determine big contribution adds.

References:

1. Желтухина М.Р. Комплексная судебная экспертиза: психолого-лингвистический аспект // Юрислингвистика-11: Право как дискурс, текст и слово: межвуз. сб. науч. тр. / Под ред. Н.Д. Голева и К.И. Бринева; Кемеровский гос. ун-т. – Кемерово, 2011. – С. 355.
2. Желтухина М.Р. Тропологическая суггестивность массмедиа-ного дискурса: о проблеме речевого воздействия тропов в языке СМИ. – М.– Волгоград: ПринТerra, 2003.
3. <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/kompleksnaya-sudebnaya-ekspertiza-psihologo-lingvisticheskiy-aspekt-1/viewer>. [21.06.2023].
4. https://siberiaexpert.ucoz.ru/publ/konferencija_2010/doklad_s_obsuzhdeniem_na_sajte/z_heltukhina_m_r_kompleksnaja_sudebnaja_ekspertiza_psikhologo_lingvisticheskij_aspekt/2-1-0-66 . [20. 06. 2023].

